

Table 1. Reaction of 14-d-old rice seedlings to infiltration with *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* strains.

Cultivar	Reaction ^a	
	PXO99A	PXO86
IR-BB10	W	HR
IR-BB21	W	W
IR24	W	W

^aW = water soaking, HR = hypersensitive reaction.

Table 2. Length of lesions induced by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* strains on adult rice plants 15 d after inoculation.

Cultivar	Plant age (d)	Lesion length ^a (cm)	
		PXO99A	PXO86
IR-BB10	45	14.3 a	1.0 b
IR-BB10	60	14.9 a	1.9 b
IR-BB21	45	1.4 b	2.3 b
IR-BB21	60	2.2 b	2.7 b
IR24	45	14.1 a	12.8 a
IR24	60	13.8 a	14.2 a

^aIn the same column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly ($P=0.01$) different according to Fisher's protected LSD.

growing certain strains of *E. coli*. It contains (per liter) 12 g bacto tryptone, 24 g yeast extract, 4 ml glycerol, 2.31 g KH_2PO_4 , and 12.5 g KH_2PO_4 . Cells were collected by centrifugation and resuspended in sterile water to obtain an inoculum concentration of 10^8 cfu/ml.

Fifteen plants of each cultivar were inoculated with strain PXO86 or strain PXO99A. Adult plants were inoculated at 45 or 60 d after seeding (DAS) using the leaf-clip method. Seedlings were inoculated at 14 DAS using the leaf-clip method or by localized infiltration of bacteria into leaves.

Plant reaction to Xoo was measured 4 d after inoculation (DAI) for seedlings. Susceptibility is indicated by water soaking reaction and resistance by hypersensitive reaction. Reactions of adult plants were assessed by measuring lesion length 15 DAI for 20 leaf samples per cultivar-strain combination. All experiments were conducted at least twice.

All cultivars at the seedling stage were susceptible to strain PXO99A, and IR-BB21 and IR24 were susceptible to strain PXO86 (Table 1). A hypersensitive

resistance response was observed on IR-BB10 inoculated with PXO86.

Lesion lengths on IR24 adult plants inoculated with PXO99A or PXO86 were typical of those for a susceptible reaction (Table 2). Lesion lengths on IR-BB10 inoculated with PXO99A were similar to those on IR24, but lesions induced by PXO86 on IR-BB10 were significantly shorter than those on IR24. Lesions induced by either Xoo race on adult plants

of IR-BB21 were significantly shorter than those observed on susceptible IR24 (Table 2).

Adult rice plants resistant to Xoo have markedly shorter lesions than do susceptible cultivars. These results indicate that the *Xa-21* resistance locus confers adult plant resistance to Xoo, but seedlings containing this locus are not appreciably resistant to the BB pathogen. ■

Virus detection in varieties resistant to tungro (RTD)

R. C. Cabunagan, Z. M. Flores, E. C. Coloquio, and H. Koganezawa, IRRI

Rice varieties Utri Merah (IRGC 16680) and Balimau Putih (IRGC 17204) do not show clear RTD symptoms even if infected. We traced the infection of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in inoculated plants by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) for 5 wk. Varieties TKM6 (resistant to RTSV), Gam Pai 30-12-15 (resistant to vector), and TN1 (susceptible) served as checks.

About 80 plants/variety were planted individually in clay pots, enclosed in mylar cages, and inoculated at 21 d

after sowing using 5 *Nephotettix virescens* adults/plant for a 24-h inoculation access time. We took a 4-cm-long sample weekly from the 2d or 3d youngest expanded leaf of each plant. The samples were homogenized in 0.1 M phosphate buffer containing 0.14 M NaCl and 0.05% tween 20 at 10× dilution. Samples were tested following the normal ELISA procedure.

Utri Merah and Balimau Putih had a relatively high RTBV infection at 1 wk after inoculation (WAI). We detected RTBV in some plants only at 2 WAI; later, RTBV became undetectable in these infected plants (see table). The concentration of RTBV examined by ELISA was always lower in these varieties than in other varieties.

Detection of RTBV in some rice varieties by ELISA at 5 weekly intervals after inoculation (WAI).

Detection pattern of RTBV in individual plants ^a at given WAI					Plants (no.) showing detection pattern in				
1	2	3	4	5	Balimau Putih	Utri Merah	TKM6	Gam Pai 30-12-15	TN1
+	+	+	+	+	2	0	28	7	78
-	+	+	+	+	0	0	48	37	0
-	-	+	+	+	0	0	1	9	2
+	-	-	-	-	40	45	0	0	0
+	+	-	-	-	16	7	0	0	0
+	+	+	-	-	1	0	0	0	0
+	-	+	-	-	1	0	0	0	0
+	-	-	-	+	1	0	0	0	0
+	+	+	-	+	1	0	0	0	0
-	+	-	-	-	8	5	0	0	0
-	-	-	-	-	8	23	2	27	0
Total					79	80	79	80	80

^a+ = positive detection and - = negative detection in individual plants at each WAI. For example, ++ --- means that RTBV was detected at 1 and 2 WAI, but not at 3-5 WAI in the same plant.

RTBV was, however, detectable in TKM6, Gam Pai 30-12-15, and TN1 throughout the period after its detection. The results indicate that the virus

concentration in Utri Merah and Balimau Putih was reduced over time to below the level of detection and is the reason why past tests done at 3-4 WAI showed low

infection rates of RTBV. The results also suggest that Utri Merah and Balimau

Relationship between phenylalanine ammonialase (PAL) activity and blast (BI) resistance in rice

Chen Zhang and Chen Qifeng, Institute of Genetics and Crop Breeding, Fujian Agricultural College, Fuzhou 350002, China

We randomly selected seedlings of 30 rice cultivars at the three-leaf stage. They were surface-sterilized in 0.1% HgCl₂ for 5 min at room temperature, and then

Relationship between BI resistance scores and PAL activity in rice seedlings.

Cultivar	Score ^a	PAL activity (OD ₂₃₀ /g fresh wt per h)
Toride 1	0	0.435
Zhaiyeqing 8	1	0.429
Xiangzaoxian 1	1	0.416
IR52	2	0.423
IR62	3	0.431
Sanerai	3	0.423
Jinwan 1	3	0.421
Jinyou 1	3	0.417
Yangdao 2	3	0.416
IR29	3	0.389
Correlation coefficient		-0.4475 ns ^b
Teqing	4	0.420
Zhefu 802	4	0.404
IR58	4	0.400
Erjiufeng	4	0.393
Zaoxian 143	4	0.390
Lunhui 422	4	0.387
6188	4	0.372
M112	5	0.378
77-175	5	0.345
Jinxi 14	6	0.381
Hongyun 33	6	0.381
Jinzhao 6	6	0.363
Erjiuai	6	0.346
73-07	6	0.342
Shenghong 16	7	0.374
22	7	0.359
Guichao 2	8	0.353
Menggudao	9	0.325
Hong 410	9	0.314
LJXTHG	9	0.309
Correlation coefficient		-0.8398*** ^c

^aBased on SES scale of 0-9. ^bNonsignificant at 5% probability level. ^cSignificant at 1% probability level.

rinsed five times in sterile distilled water. Leaves were cut off and crushed by hammering individually in boric acid buffer (pH 8.8), each liter supplemented with 0.5 g polyvinyl pyrrolidone. The mixture was centrifuged three times at 5,000 rpm for 25 min at 4 °C. Then 0.5 ml of the supernatant was mixed in a test tube with 3.5 ml of a reaction mixture that contained 20 mmol L-Phe 2 ml/liter and allowed to rest for 60 min at 30 °C. The absorbance of the mixture at 290 nm was recorded using a UV 120-02-01 model Ultraviolet-spectrophotometer

(Shimadzu Ltd. Co., Japan). The experiment was replicated four times.

The correlation coefficient was nonsignificant at 5% probability level for PAL activity and BI resistance in rice cultivars (*Standard evaluation system for rice* [SES] scores of 0-3) on the qualitative scale based on lesion type, but it was significant at 1% probability (scores of 4-9) on the quantitative scale based on the percentage of leaf area affected. This indicates that PAL activity increased as the BI resistance score decreased from 4 to 9 (see table). ■

Efficiency of natural selection for bacterial sheath rot (BSR) in bulked families

J. P. Tilquin, Crop Improvement Department, Agricultural Faculty, University of Burundi, P.O. Box 2940, Bujumbura; and J. F. Detry, Phytopathology Department, Institut des Sciences Agronomiques du Burundi, Burundi

BSR, induced by *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae* Tanii, Miyajima, et Akita, was earlier reported on rice only in the northern part of Hokkaido, Japan. It was discovered in Burundi in 1982. This disease has since been identified in Madagascar and Latin America in rice, sorghum, maize, and wheat. In rice, BSR causes poor panicle exertion, leading to sterility of the nonexserted part of the panicle.

BSR is particularly damaging to modern varieties with the *sd₁* gene and partially explains the poor performance of fixed varieties in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. We compared Ambalalava, a tall, fixed, variety that is well-adapted to BSR, with two F₃, F₆, F₇, and F₈ bulked populations from 1988 to 1991 at the same site at 1,550 m asl.

The two populations were grown at the site in 1987, but BSR pressure was very low. BSR incidence was measured as the percentage of partially exserted

panicles in a sample of 10 pots with three replications. Severity was estimated by the difference in weight between 25 sampled panicles with and without disease (mean of three replications).

Yield loss is measured by the incidence multiplied by severity of BSR.

1. BSR incidence in Burundi, 1988-91.

2. BSR severity in Burundi, 1988-91.

